

Accurate LiDAR-based Semantic Classification for Powerline Inspection

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Abstract. Mandatory power grid inspection includes the periodic measurement of the distances between vegetation and electrical assets. This paper presents an efficient and accurate method for segmenting LiDAR-based maps leveraging both LiDAR reflectivity and point cloud geometric information to classify points into *Powerline*, *Tower*, *Vegetation*, and *Soil*. It is based on two steps: 1) initial online segmentation using the LiDAR reflectivity and local point cloud spatial distribution and 2) off-line segmentation refinement using the cloud global spatial distribution. The method obtains a very accurate classification and enables accurate measurement of distances from vegetation to the electrical assets. Its performance was evaluated in sets of powerline inspection experiments in two power grid scenarios with different conditions and vegetation.

Keywords: LiDAR segmentation · Unmanned Aerial Systems

1 Introduction

There is a strong demand to develop automated cost-effective solutions to automatize powerline inspection tasks. Power grid inspection has been traditionally performed by teams of workers climbing or using cranes or man-fits to access the electric lines and assets, involving extensive manpower in highly dangerous environments. One mandatory inspection task is to measure the distances between vegetation and the electrical lines and towers. Different aerial vehicles including manned and unmanned helicopters [1], Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) vehicles [2], and quadrotors [3] have been used. Quadrotors have been endowed with capacity of perching on powerlines to recharge their batteries [4] to extend flight endurance. These vehicles first collect 3D LiDAR (Light Detection And Ranging) point clouds and images of the surroundings of the powerline. Later, days or weeks after the recording, the registered data is processed to build vegetation maps and measure vegetation-power assets distances. This procedure is very inefficient, and requires repeating data gathering if in the analysis the collected data is found to be of insufficient quality for the inspection.

Some mapping techniques capable of online obtaining 3D maps for powerline inspection have been developed, see e.g. [5]. This paper proposes an efficient LiDAR-only processing method for segmenting 3D powerline maps and extracting accurate measurements of the distances between vegetation and powerlines

and electrical towers. The method segments *Powerlines*, *Towers*, *Vegetation*, and *Soil* by leveraging the LiDAR’s point cloud reflectivity and spatial distribution in two steps. First, the LiDAR scans are online processed classifying points into the four possible classes. Second, a global refinement step enhances the online segmentation to ensure accurate distance measurements. Finally, the proposed method measures the distance between each vegetation point and the nearest point of a powerline or tower. Potential risks are assessed according to different distance ranges, which can be customized depending on the requirements. The proposed scheme is very accurate, robust for everyday operation, and efficient. It has been implemented in C++ using PCL and ROS Noetic, and validated in powerline inspection experiments conducted in different environments and type of vegetation.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly summarizes the main works related to the paper. Section 3 describes the proposed method and its components. The experimental validation is presented in Section 4. Finally, Section 5 closes the paper and highlights the main future research.

2 Related Work

Significant R&D effort has been devoted to automatic object segmentation for powerline inspection. LiDARs and cameras are the most widely applied sensors. Most segmentation methods for powerline inspection are based on the geometry of the point clouds. Work [6] proposes a learning method based on Markov Random Fields to assign semantic labels to point cloud segments. Work [7] segments powerlines using skeleton structure extraction and construction of 3D voxels. Other methods use heuristic information leveraging geometric fitting. For instance, [8] proposed an unified energy function over objectiveness and geometry fitting in indoor and office environments.

In recent years Deep Learning (DL) has been applied to powerline segmentation. Work [9] segments LiDAR point clouds into categories ground, vegetation, electrical tower, and building using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). Work [10] proposes the use of a global-local Graph Attention CNN to segment towers, powerlines, low vegetation, and others. Although these methods have solid performance, they have high computational cost that constraints online onboard execution. In addition, DL requires labour-intensive training stages and large annotated datasets, which involve additional operational difficulties.

Some few methods complement the LiDAR point cloud geometrical information with reflectivity information. Work [11] leverages the LiDAR point reflectivity to detect and classify traffic signs using an optimized intensity threshold and contour recognition. Work [12] models the LiDAR reflection return to determine the properties of the scanned surface. Other methods perform the segmentation using mainly visual information. Work [13] uses a multilayer perceptron for tower detection and classification using two multi-layer perceptron neural networks. Work [14] applies DL-based segmentation to RGB images used to create the point cloud and back-projects the pixel class in segmented images

onto the LiDAR 3D points. Work [15] uses DL scheme based on featured pyramid networks and YOLACT to detect electrical elements. Work [16] proposed a deep neural Fully Convolutional Network (FCN). There are also methods that combine point cloud geometry and visual information. Work [17] fuses features extracted from the RGB image together with LiDAR data and feed them to a CNN for object segmentation. Work [18] shows that fusing LiDAR data and visual images improves the detection performance especially at long ranges.

Despite the significant effort, the high computational cost of existing LiDAR-based segmentation methods prevents their use for onboard online inspection.

3 Method

The proposed approach adapts the method described in [19] to separate the map points in four different classes: *Powerline*, *Tower*, *Vegetation*, and *Soil*. Similarly to [19], to distinguish among each category, we consider point cloud spatial distribution and take advantage of the fact that metallic and no metallic points tend to present different reflectivity values (r). Despite the remarkable results achieved by [19], its geometrical analysis of the metallic points is based solely on their local neighborhood. Object segmentation is used to measure the distances between objects classified as *Vegetation*, and *Powerline* and *Tower*. A single misclassified *Tower* or *Powerline* point can cause unacceptable errors in those distances. In general, it is not possible to ensure accurate classification of every point using solely local geometry, and online segmentation does not take advantage of the global geometry of the environment, that is required to refine the segmentation. Hence, to avoid these problems, our method includes a post processing step that considers global geometrical information to refine point classification. The proposed method consists of two steps. First, *Online Segmentation* processes in real-time consecutive scans to obtain a coarse classification the points among the four classes. Second, *Full Map Refinement* step refines the initial classifications by identifying the different elements of the map and checking the fulfillment of different properties related to their geometry and distribution.

3.1 Online Segmentation

Figure 1 shows the processing pipeline of this stage. First, N consecutive LiDAR scans are accumulated to obtain a denser representation of the environment. Online segmentation starts with the extraction of soil points, given their predominant presence in the scans. To achieve this, the accumulated points are fitted to a plane using RANSAC algorithm and those contained in the surface are classified as *Soil*.

Once the soil is segmented, the remaining points are first analysed by their reflectivity. Points with reflectivity below T_r are considered as metallic points, otherwise they are classified as *Vegetation*. Next, taking advantage of spatial geometrical information, the points belonging to class *Powerline* should be those

Fig. 1. Processing pipeline of *Online Segmentation*.

that are distributed most distinctly along a single direction within the set of metallic points. Thus, by conducting a Principal Component Analysis (PCA), a linearity metric l can be computed with the resulting eigenvalues, see Equation 1. For each potential metallic point p_i , PCA is applied to the set of potential metallic points, whose distance to p_i is below a value R_l , see Equation 2. Points p_i with high linearity, $l > T_l$, are classified as *Powerline*.

$$l = \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_2 + \lambda_3} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{PCA}\{\{n : \|p_i - n\| \leq R_l\}\}, \forall i \quad (2)$$

Finally, the remaining points are a combination of tower and vegetation points. We rely on the predominance of high reflectivity points around true vegetation points to perform an initial segmentation of towers. For each point p , we obtain the sets n_h and n_l with the points whose distance to p is below a value R_t and have respectively high and low reflectivity values. Then, we calculate the metric $\phi = \frac{|n_h|}{|n_l|}$. If point p has $\phi > T_\phi$, it is classified as *Tower*. Otherwise, p is classified as *Vegetation*. *Online Segmentation* provides an initial classification of every point from every LiDAR scan, which is then refined in *Full Map Refinement* to achieve an accurate final segmented map.

3.2 Full Map Refinement

Given the large number of points produced by the soil and the consistency of the planar soil hypothesis, the soil segmentation performed in *Online Segmentation* is significantly accurate and robust. *Full Map Refinement* does not perform refinements on the soil cloud; it only downsamples it to reduce the computational cost and enhance visualization. Conversely, the input vegetation, powerline, and tower clouds (obtained by *Online Segmentation*) present a large number of misclassifications since the local information used in *Online Segmentation* is not enough to ensure accurate segmentation. The processing scheme of *Full Map*

Refinement is shown in Figure 2. First, it processes the input powerline and tower clouds (resulting from *Online Segmentation*) to reject the points that are not caused by powerlines or towers. This results in the ensured powerlines cloud and the ensured towers cloud. Second, these two ensured clouds are used to accurately classify all the points in all the input clouds.

Fig. 2. Processing pipeline of *Full Map Refinement*.

The input powerline cloud created by *Online Segmentation* includes misclassified vegetation and tower points. All the vegetation points in this cloud are rejected by obtaining clusters and studying their geometry with PCA. A clustering method based on Euclidean distance is applied to obtain clusters of nearby points. Next, the class of each cluster is assigned. Powerline clusters can be easily distinguished from vegetation clusters using PCA given their very high linearity. Hence, all the clusters which meet the linearity condition $l > T_{el}$ are merged and classified as *Powerline*. The rest of the points are removed. The resulting cloud (ensured powerlines) has no vegetation but can include some few points originated by towers. Although most of them are discarded in this step, some tower points might have been included in the cloud. These misclassifications are rejected after processing of the tower cloud, which is described as follows.

Most misclassifications in the input tower cloud correspond to vegetation. Since towers have linear geometry, they can be distinguished from vegetation by also using clustering and PCA. The clustering is also based on the Euclidean distance. However, it is not possible to reject all vegetation clusters using only PCA-based criteria since tower clusters do not exhibit the same level of linearity as powerline clusters. To distinguish them, we exploit the fact that towers are in contact with powerlines, and add an additional condition regarding the connectivity with powerlines. Joining both conditions, a cluster is ensured as *Tower* if it satisfies: 1) a linearity higher than T_{et} , and 2) a distance to a powerline point below d_{et} . The resulting cloud is the ensured towers cloud.

Once we have obtained the ensured powerlines and towers clouds, they are used to classify every point in all the input clouds (resulting from *Online Segmentation*). The processing of the input powerline cloud is as follows. For each

point we compute the distance to the nearest point in the ensured towers cloud. If that distance is lower than a refinement distance d_r , the point is definitely classified as *Tower*. Otherwise, it is considered as caused by a powerline and, classified as *Powerline*. The processing of the input vegetation cloud is similar. If the distance from a point in the input vegetation cloud to its closest point in the towers cloud is lower than d_r , it is classified as *Tower*. Otherwise, it is classified as *Vegetation*. The processing of the input tower cloud is similar –and not repeated for brevity.

Lastly, we perform a global filtering to correct minor misclassifications. The vegetation cloud can include points caused by grass that appear surrounded by soil points and disturb visualization. They are simply removed. The vegetation cloud also includes some spurious points at the locations of powerlines and towers caused by the effect of surface roughness on reflectivity. We perform a statistical fashion filter to re-assign the class of these points with the most frequent class among its local neighbourhood (points within a distance lower than d_r).

4 Validation

The proposed segmentation method was implemented in C++ using PCL and ROS Noetic, and validated in different environments with the *LR-M* aerial robot developed by the GRVC Robotics Lab from the University of Seville, see Figure 3. Based on the DJI Matrice 600 platform, *LR-M* is equipped with a Livox Horizon 3D LiDAR pointing at a pitch angle of -40° . The input of the proposed method is the registered LiDAR clouds of the mapping algorithm FAST-LIO2 [20], which showed the best performance in [5]. The parameters mentioned in Section 3 were set as shown in Table 1. Several experiments were conducted in different challenging scenarios: Doñana National Park (Andalusia, Spain), in which there is a tower with some sensors and solar panels, and ATLAS Flight Test Center (Villacarrillo, Jaen, Spain), which includes a plastic hanging from a powerline to emulate a foreign object in contact with the powerline. Figure 4 shows the resulting semantic map in one experiment in each site. After segmentation, we measured the distances between vegetation points and tower and powerline points. The vegetation points whose distance to powerline points or tower points is lower than 10 m are shown in red colour, reflecting high risk. And those with distance between 10 and 20 m are shown in yellow, medium risk.

Accurate distance measurement necessarily requires very robust point classification. We compared the results of our method with a ground truth obtained by manually labelling the point clouds. Figure 5 shows the resulting confusion matrices in both experiments. The diagonal of these matrices has values very close to 100% evidencing the very high *True Positive* rates achieved. Remarkably for our application, the very few misclassified points only occur between soil and vegetation, or between powerlines and towers. No points caused by soil or vegetation are erroneously classified as powerlines or towers. Conversely, for powerline and towers classification, there are only some scarce points representing in the worst case 0.23% of misclassifications between these and soil or vegetation.

Fig. 3. *LR-M* aerial robot used in the experiments.

Errors in distinguishing within powerlines and towers occur only at points very close to their intersection.

Online		Refinement	
Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
N	5	T_{el}	0.99
T_r	13	T_{et}	0.68
T_l	0.90	d_{et}	0.05 m
T_ϕ	4	d_r	1.5 m
R_l	0.4 m		
R_t	1.5 m		

Table 1. Values of the method parameters used in the experimental results.

5 Conclusions

This paper presented a processing method for efficient LiDAR-only point cloud segmentation in powerline inspection. The method classifies each LiDAR point into classes *Powerline*, *Tower*, *Vegetation*, and *Soil* by using point cloud reflectivity and spatial distribution. It consists of two steps. First, the points are online classified using LiDAR reflectivity and local spatial distribution information. Second, the method leverages the point cloud global spatial distribution to refine the initial segmentation ensuring accurate classification. The method has been experimentally evaluated in two powerline environments with different types of objects and vegetation. It achieved an exceptional classification accuracy in which no points caused by soil or vegetation are misclassified as powerlines

Fig. 4. Segmented maps and automatic distance measurement results in two scenarios: top) Doñana National Park, and bottom) ATLAS Flight Test Center

		Predicted Class			
		S	V	T	L
True Class	S	99.33%	0.67%	0%	0%
	V	0%	100%	0%	0%
	T	0%	0.23%	99.77%	0%
	L	0%	0%	15.58%	84.42%

Doñana National Park

		Predicted Class			
		S	V	T	L
True Class	S	99.05%	0.95%	0%	0%
	V	4.36%	95.64%	0%	0%
	T	0.06%	0.13%	99.81%	0%
	L	0%	0.01%	2.74%	97.25%

ATLAS Flight Test Center

Fig. 5. Resulting confusion matrices from full map segmentation in two scenarios: left) Doñana National Park, and right) ATLAS Flight Test Center

or towers, hence enabling accurate automatic measurement of distances from vegetation to the electrical assets. Extending the validation to a wider range of power grids environments is object of current development.

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References

1. H. Li, B. Wang, L. Liu, G. Tian, T. Zheng, and J. Zhang, “The design and application of smartcopter: An unmanned helicopter based robot for transmission line inspection,” in *Chinese Automation Congress*, 2013, pp. 697–702.
2. W. de Britto Vidal Filho and A. M. de Almeida Pinto, “Vtol aerial robot for inspection of transmission line,” in *Proc.s Int. Conf. on Applied Robotics for the Power Industry*, 2014, pp. 1–4.
3. K. Takaya, H. Ohta, V. Kroumov, K. Shibayama, and M. Nakamura, “Development of uav system for autonomous power line inspection,” in *Int. Conf on System Theory, Control and Computing*, 2019, pp. 762–767.
4. J. Paneque, J. Martínez-de Dios, A. Ollero, D. Hanover, S. Sun, A. Romero, and D. Scaramuzza, “Perception-aware perching on powerlines with multirotors,” *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 3077–3084, 2022.
5. J. Paneque, V. Valseca, J. R. Martínez-de Dios, and A. Ollero, “Autonomous reactive lidar-based mapping for powerline inspection,” in *Int. Conf on Unmanned Aircraft Systems*, 2022.

6. Y. Perez-Perez, M. Golparvar-Fard, and K. El-Rayes, "Segmentation of point clouds via joint semantic and geometric features for 3d modeling of the built environment," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 125, p. 103584, 2021.
7. J. Yang and Z. Kang, "Voxel-based extraction of transmission lines from airborne lidar point cloud data," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, vol. 11, no. 10, pp. 3892–3904, 2018.
8. T. T. Pham, T.-T. Do, N. Sinderhauf, and I. Reid, "Scenecut: Joint geometric and object segmentation for indoor scenes," in *IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Autom.* IEEE, 2018, pp. 3213–3220.
9. S. Pu, L. Xie, M. Ji, Y. Zhao, W. Liu, L. Wang, F. Yang, and D. Qiu, "Real-time powerline corridor inspection by edge computing of uav lidar data," *The Int. Archives of Photogr., Remote Sensing & Spatial Information Sciences*, vol. 42, pp. 547–551, 2019.
10. C. Wen, X. Li, X. Yao, L. Peng, and T. Chi, "Airborne lidar point cloud classification with global-local graph attention convolution neural network," *ISPRS Journal of Photog. & Remote Sensing*, vol. 173, pp. 181–194, 2021.
11. B. Riveiro, L. Díaz-Vilariño, B. Conde-Carnero, M. Soilán, and P. Arias, "Automatic segmentation and shape-based classification of retro-reflective traffic signs from mobile lidar data," *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 295–303, 2015.
12. A. Tatoglu and K. Pochiraju, "Point cloud segmentation with lidar reflection intensity behavior," in *IEEE Int. Conf. Robot. Autom.*, 2012, pp. 786–790.
13. C. Sampedro, C. Martinez, A. Chauhan, and P. Campoy, "A supervised approach to electric tower detection and classification for power line inspection," in *Int. Joint Conf. on Neural Networks*, 2014, pp. 1970–1977.
14. M. WuDunn, J. Dunn, and A. Zakhor, "Point cloud segmentation using rgb drone imagery," in *IEEE Int. Conf. on Image Process.*, 2020, pp. 2750–2754.
15. S. Vemula and M. Frye, "Real-time powerline detection system for an unmanned aircraft system," in *Int. Conf. on Systems, Man, & Cybernetics*, 2020, pp. 4493–4497.
16. B. Li, C. Chen, S. Dong, and J. Qiao, "Transmission line detection in aerial images: An instance segmentation approach based on multitask neural networks," *Signal Processing: Image Communication*, vol. 96, p. 116278, 2021.
17. G. Krispel, M. Opitz, G. Waltner, H. Possegger, and H. Bischof, "Fuseseg: Lidar point cloud segmentation fusing multi-modal data," in *Proc. of the IEEE/CVF Winter Conf. on App. of Computer Vision*, 2020, pp. 1874–1883.
18. G. P. Meyer, J. Charland, D. Hegde, A. Laddha, and C. Vallespi-Gonzalez, "Sensor fusion for joint 3d object detection and semantic segmentation," in *Proc. IEEE/CVF Conf. on Computer Vision & Pattern Recognition Workshops*, 2019.
19. V. Valseca, J. Paneque, J. Martínez-de Dios, and A. Ollero, "Real-time lidar-based semantic classification for powerline inspection," in *Int. Conf. on Unmanned Aircraft Systems*, 2022, pp. 478–486.
20. W. Xu, Y. Cai, D. He, J. Lin, and F. Zhang, "Fast-lio2: Fast direct lidar-inertial odometry," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 38, no. 4, pp. 2053–2073, 2022.